

101136318 – SUSTAIN-HTA
Support Utilisation of Sustainable and
Tailored Innovative methods for HTA

SUSTAIN^{HTA}

D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods

Lead contributor	Saif Elayan (1 – UU), Wim Goettsch (1 – UU) and Karen Facey (1 – UU)
Other contributors	Shane Collins (15 – NICE), Dalia Dawoud (15 – NICE), Carlo Federici (2 – UB), Zoe Garrett (15 – NICE), Andrea Greco (2 – UB), Wija Oortwijn (5 – RUMC), Peter Rijnbeek (3 – EMC), Fatima Salih (15 – NICE), and Liza van Mun (5 – RUMC).
Work Package	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation
Due date	31/03/2025
Delivery date	31/03/2025
Deliverable type	R
Dissemination level	PU – Public

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation	Version: 3.0	
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch	Dissemination: PU	2/16

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DOCUMENT HISTORY	3
DEFINITIONS	4
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1 Introduction.....	7
2 Methods.....	8
2.1 Identification of Completed EU-Funded Projects.....	8
2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria	8
2.3 Data Extraction and Database Development	9
3 Results.....	9
3.1 Overview of the Database.....	10
4 Discussion	11
5 Next Steps	13
References	15

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation	Version: 3.0	
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch	Dissemination: PU	3/16

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	6 March 2025	First Draft
V2.0	11 March 2025	Second Draft for Steering Committee Review
V3.0	31 March 2025	Final Version

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 4/16

DEFINITIONS

Partners of the SUSTAIN-HTA Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

1. **UU** Universiteit Utrecht (Netherlands)
2. **UB** Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi (Italy)
3. **EMC** Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam (Netherlands)
4. **ZIN** Zorginstituut Nederland (Netherlands)
5. **RUMC** Stichting Radboud Universitair Medisch Centrum (Netherlands)
6. **SRI** Syreon Kutato Intezet Korlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag (Hungary)
7. **OSTEBA** Fundacion Vasca de Innovacion e Investigacion Sanitarias (Spain)
8. **GetReal I** GetReal Institute (Netherlands)
9. **SYNAPSE** Research Management Partners (Spain)
10. **NIPN** Nemzeti Nepegészségügyi és Gyógyszerészeti Központ (Hungary)
11. **AGE.NA.S** Agenzia Nazionale per i Servizi Sanitari Regionali (Italy)
12. **AQUAS** Agencia de Qualitat i Avaluació Sanitaries de Catalunya (Spain)
13. **NOMA** Statens Legemiddelverk (Norway)
14. **UCSC** Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (Italy)
15. **NICE** National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (United Kingdom)

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency for the undertaking of the SUSTAIN-HTA project (101136318).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The SUSTAIN-HTA Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst SUSTAIN-HTA partners for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation	Version: 3.0	
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch	Dissemination: PU	5/16

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020
HRQoL	Health-Related Quality of Life
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
HTACG	Member State Coordination Group on HTA
IHI	Innovative Health Initiative
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
RUM	Resource Use Measurement
RWD	Real-World Data
RWE	Real-World Evidence
SUSTAIN-HS	SUSTAIN-HTA Horizon Scanning
SUSTAIN-OBS	SUSTAIN-HTA Methods Observatory
SUSTAIN-SB	SUSTAIN-HTA Sandbox Environment
WP1	Work Package 1

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 6/16

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The European Union (EU) has made substantial investments in advancing health technology assessment (HTA), yet the adoption of innovative HTA methods and tools by HTA bodies remains limited. The reasons behind this limited uptake of methods and tools are not fully understood but may stem from insufficient dissemination, implementation barriers, concerns about applicability in HTA practice, or misalignment with the needs of HTA bodies. SUSTAIN-HTA aims to bridge this gap by assessing the methodological needs of European HTA bodies and mapping them to relevant innovative HTA methods. To this end, Work Package 1 is spearheading two key initiatives: 1) a horizon-scanning tool (SUSTAIN-HS) to monitor the evolving methodological needs of European HTA bodies (Task 1.3); and 2) a methods observatory (SUSTAIN-OBS) to identify and categorise innovative HTA methods and tools (Task 1.5). This report constitutes the initial phase of Task 1.5, presenting an inventory of HTA methods and tools developed in projects funded under Horizon Europe and its predecessor, Horizon 2020, as well as under the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) and its predecessor, the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI). The inventory focuses specifically on projects completed within the past five years to ensure relevance to current HTA practices.

A multi-step approach was employed to identify relevant research projects. Consortium members, drawing on their involvement in multiple EU-funded initiatives, reported projects known to them that had contributed to the development of HTA methods and tools. This internal effort was complemented by consultations with members of the Expert and Stakeholder forums. Project outputs were sourced from the EU Funding & Tenders Portal and official project websites. Predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied to ensure the methodological relevance of selected outputs to HTA. The identified methods and tools were catalogued in an Excel-based database, capturing project-level details, method- and tool-specific attributes, and classification according to the SUSTAIN-HTA taxonomy developed in Task 1.2.

The review identified five Horizon 2020 projects and two IMI-funded projects that contributed to the development of HTA methods. Of the 348 outputs (e.g., deliverables and publications) originating from these projects, 99 met the inclusion criteria, resulting in 55 distinct methods and tools. Among these, 78% were derived from the Horizon 2020 projects, while 22% were developed within the IMI initiatives. The methodological focus of the identified methods and tools varied, with 47% addressing clinical effectiveness, 35% relating to costs and economic evaluation, and the remainder covering organisational aspects, safety, and broader issues extending beyond HTA. These methods and tools spanned a range of methodological areas, including real-world evidence (35%), predictive modelling (13%), health-related quality of life (11%), costing and resource use (11%), and heterogeneity in treatment effects and cost-effectiveness (7%).

Several of the identified methods and tools align with the methodological needs of European HTA bodies outlined in Task 1.3. This alignment underscores the potential of SUSTAIN-OBS as a structured and accessible resource, enabling HTA bodies to identify methods and tools that meet their needs and supporting the integration of innovative methods into real-world settings.

Looking ahead, the observatory will be expanded to incorporate methods and tools emerging from ongoing Horizon Europe/2020 and IMI/IHI projects; EU projects funded under other schemes; HTA bodies; international HTA-related organisations; and peer-reviewed literature. An online tool will also be developed to enhance accessibility, allowing users to locate and retrieve information on relevant methods efficiently. Engagement with HTA bodies and the Expert Forum will continue to ensure the observatory remains a dynamic and evolving resource for methodological advancements in HTA.

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation	Version: 3.0	
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch	Dissemination: PU	7/16

1 Introduction

Health technology assessment (HTA) is ‘a multidisciplinary process that uses explicit methods to determine the value of a health technology at different points in its lifecycle’. This value may be assessed by examining the intended and unintended consequences of using a health technology compared to existing alternatives, across several dimensions including clinical effectiveness, safety, cost and economic implications, as well as ethical, social, cultural, legal, organisational, and environmental aspects (O’Rourke et al., 2020).

The European Union (EU) has made considerable investments in HTA through various research projects aimed at advancing scientific methods. These investments are intended to enhance decision-making in healthcare by improving the evaluation of health technologies. However, despite the development of numerous innovative HTA methods by EU projects and other learned consortia and academia, their adoption by HTA bodies remains limited. The reasons for this limited uptake are not well understood, though several factors may contribute to the challenge. Potential explanations include insufficient visibility and dissemination of new methods and tools, practical barriers to implementation, methodological concerns regarding their applicability in HTA practice, or a mismatch between the methods/tools developed and the actual needs of HTA bodies.

To address these challenges, SUSTAIN-HTA—a Horizon Europe Coordination and Support Action (CSA)—has been established to assess the methodological needs of European HTA bodies and align them with innovative HTA methods and tools, particularly those developed through EU-funded projects. By systematically identifying HTA bodies’ needs and mapping them to methodological innovations, SUSTAIN-HTA strives to facilitate the adoption of methods that address these needs, thereby improving the rigor, consistency, and impact of HTA practices across Europe.

Work Package 1 (WP1) is dedicated to exploring these issues. Task 1.3 will establish a continuous horizon-scanning tool (SUSTAIN-HS) to identify and monitor the evolving methodological needs of European HTA bodies. In parallel, Task 1.5 will develop a methods observatory (SUSTAIN-OBS) to systematically identify and categorise innovative HTA methods and tools. In Task 1.6, the methodological needs identified through horizon scanning will be considered alongside the innovative methods catalogued in the observatory to prioritise those most relevant to HTA bodies. Subsequently, the prioritised methods will be tested for implementation as case studies within the SUSTAIN-HTA Sandbox Environment (SUSTAIN-SB).

This report represents the first step in Task 1.5, focusing on identifying the methods and tools developed by EU-funded research projects that concluded within the past five years (i.e., between

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 8/16

2020 and 2024). Specifically, the report focuses on projects funded under Horizon Europe and its predecessor Horizon 2020, or under the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) and its predecessor, the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI). The goal is to provide a comprehensive inventory of these methods and tools, ensuring their visibility and accessibility to HTA bodies. In subsequent annual reports, this mapping exercise will be expanded to include ongoing Horizon Europe and IHI projects, EU projects funded under other schemes, as well as peer-reviewed literature and relevant outputs from HTA bodies, HTA bodies' collaborations, HTA/payer collaborations, and international (professional) HTA-related organisations. This continuous, multi-source approach will help ensure that the observatory remains an up-to-date repository of methodological advancements in HTA.

2 Methods

2.1 Identification of Completed EU-Funded Projects

The first step involved systematically identifying Horizon Europe/2020 and IMI/IHI projects that had produced methods or tools relevant to HTA. As mentioned earlier, the scope of this report was limited to projects that concluded within the past five years to ensure the relevance to current HTA practices. A multi-step approach was employed to identify these projects. First, during WP1 meetings, consortium members—drawing on their broad involvement in numerous EU-funded initiatives—reported projects known to them that had contributed to the development of HTA methodologies. This internal identification was complemented by input from members of the project's Expert and Stakeholder forums, collected during forum meetings. This coordinated approach aimed to ensure a comprehensive mapping of relevant projects and to minimise the risk of omitting significant initiatives.

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Following the identification of relevant projects, a set of predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria was applied to assess the eligibility of their outputs (e.g., deliverables and publications) for inclusion in this assessment. These criteria were formulated to ensure that only outputs of methodological relevance and applicability to HTA were retained for analysis.

- Inclusion Criteria
 - The output must present or describe a method or tool relevant to HTA.
 - The output must be accessible via the EU Funding & Tenders Portal or the official website of the project/initiative.

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 9/16

- For academic publications, the output must include a funding statement or other explicit reference linking it to the corresponding project/initiative.
- Exclusion Criteria
 - Outputs related exclusively to project management, administrative reporting, or coordination activities.
 - Outputs addressing topics that do not concern methods or tools applicable to HTA.

2.3 Data Extraction and Database Development

The data extraction process was designed to systematically collect and document information on identified HTA methods and tools. An Excel-based database was developed to serve as a structured repository for data collection and analysis. This database will be used as the background to the SUSTAIN-OBS.

To ensure comprehensive and systematic documentation, the database captured both project-related information and details specific to the method or tool reported, which may be searched upon in SUSTAIN-OBS. Project-related information included the project name, funding source, and a summary of the project’s main achievements. Information related to the reported method or tool encompassed the type of technology to which it is applicable and a description of its purpose and characteristics. Additionally, links to project outputs in which the method or tool is documented were recorded, and supplementary information relevant to its application (e.g., country of application or clinical condition) was noted when relevant.

The database was structured with a project-centric ordering to facilitate systematic data extraction, ensuring that each entry corresponded to a specific project. The reported methods and tools were also categorised according to the methodological domains and areas of HTA they address. The categorisation was underpinned by the SUSTAIN-HTA taxonomy and expanded to be in accordance with the HTA Core Model (Elayan et al., 2024; Lampe et al., 2009). To improve usability, the database was designed with integrated filtering functions, enabling dynamic reorganisation and targeted searches based on project- and method or tool-level characteristics.

3 Results

A total of five Horizon 2020 projects and two IMI projects were identified as contributing to the development of HTA methods and tools (see Table 1). From these projects, 348 documents

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 10/16

(e.g., project deliverables and publications) were retrieved. Of these, 99 met the predefined inclusion criteria and were deemed eligible for further analysis.

Table 1. Overview of Identified European HTA-Related Research Projects

Project Name	Completion Year	Project Type	Project Website
COMED	2021	Horizon 2020	www.comedh2020.eu
IMPACT HTA	2021	Horizon 2020	www.impact-hta.eu
PECUNIA	2021	Horizon 2020	www.pecunia-project.eu
GetReal*	2021	Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI)	www.getreal-initiative.eu
HEcoPerMed	2022	Horizon 2020	www.hecopermed.eu
HTx	2024	Horizon 2020	www.htx-h2020.eu
EHDEN	2024	Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI)	www.ehden.eu

* The original GetReal project (2013–2017) and the follow-up GetReal Initiative (2018–2021).

From these eligible documents, 55 distinct methods and tools were identified. Of these, 43 (78%) were developed by Horizon 2020 projects, while 12 (22%) originated from IMI initiatives. Approximately two-thirds (65%) of identified methods were non-technology-specific, meaning they were applicable to a broad range of health technologies rather than being restricted to a particular type of intervention.

In terms of methodological focus, just under half of the identified methods (47%) pertained to clinical effectiveness, while slightly more than one-third (35%) focused on costs and economic evaluation. The remaining methods addressed organisational aspects, safety, or broader issues extending beyond the traditional scope of HTA.

The identified methods and tools spanned various methodological areas. Approximately one-third (35%) were related to real-world evidence (RWE). Methods concerning predictive modelling accounted for 13%, while 11% focused on health-related quality of life (HRQoL), 11% related to costing and resource use, and 7% addressed heterogeneity issues.

3.1 Overview of the Database

The database was structured into multiple tabs to manage different categories of information, ensuring organised documentation and ease of retrieval. These tabs include:

- **Overview of Projects and Initiatives Tab:** Provides a high-level summary of each project or initiative, drawing on publicly available descriptions such as project impact summaries on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal.

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 11/16

- **Repository Tab:** Contains detailed information on each identified method or tool, including project-related details and classifications based on the SUSTAIN-HTA taxonomy. Fields in this tab include:
 - Project name
 - Funding source
 - Project status
 - Types of technology applicable
 - HTA domain classification
 - Category and type of method
 - Method/tool description
 - Geographic and clinical scope
 - Additional information on applicability
- **Abbreviations Tab:** Lists abbreviations used in the database to facilitate navigation and interpretation of database entries.

By structuring the data this way, the database provides a comprehensive and user-friendly repository for tracking and retrieving information on catalogued HTA methods and tools.

4 Discussion

This report marks the first step in establishing the SUSTAIN-HTA methods observatory to systematically identify and categorise developments in HTA methods and tools. The identification of 55 distinct methods and tools from Horizon Europe/2020 and IMI/IHI-funded initiatives underscores the significant contributions of these projects to advancing HTA methods.

The findings reveal a strong emphasis on methods and tools targeting clinical effectiveness as well as costs and economic evaluation, which reflects the continued prominence of these domains in methodological research (Germeni & Szabo, 2023). Moreover, the considerable representation of methods related to RWE signals a growing recognition of the need for methodological advancements that address challenges associated with real-world data (RWD) use in HTA (Claire et al., 2024).

Several methods and tools identified correspond to the methodological needs related to RWE use in HTA identified in Task 1.3 (Elayan et al., 2025). For instance, the HTx project published a demonstrator report showcasing the application of the target trial emulation framework to estimate the causal average treatment effect on overall survival and HRQoL for erythropoietin-stimulating agents (Bennett et al., 2024). This demonstrator outlines key considerations in designing a target

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 12/16

trial and the application of statistical models and provides an R code to carry out the analysis. Another example is the three-stage network meta-regression prediction model developed within HTx, which enables the prediction of heterogeneous treatment effects using multiple data sources, including RWE (Chalkou et al., 2024).

Multiple methods and tools for costing and resource use were identified. Most were developed through Horizon 2020 projects that concluded in 2021, funded under a research call focused on improving economic evaluation methods. This finding aligns with insights from Task 1.3, which emphasised the need for rigorous methods to assess the indirect costs and benefits of health technologies. For example, the IMPACT HTA project developed a standardised method for estimating the fiscal impact of health gains—such as productivity gains, consumption increases and potential tax revenues—to provide a more integrated view of the economic and societal impact of health technologies (Cicchetti et al., 2021). Similarly, the PECUNIA Resource Use Measurement (PECUNIA RUM) Instrument facilitates the measurement of resource use across all relevant sectors for costing from a societal perspective, including health and social care, education, (criminal) justice, productivity losses, and informal care (Pokhilenko et al., 2023).

The identification of several methods addressing heterogeneity in treatment effects and cost-effectiveness signals the growing recognition that patients may systematically vary—in a number of ways—in the benefits they derive from a health technology and/or the costs associated with its delivery (Sculpher, 2008). This aligns with the needs identified in Task 1.3, which emphasised the need for methods capable of capturing heterogeneity in treatment effects and cost-effectiveness. Furthermore, other methods identified address issues related to surrogate endpoints and indirect comparisons, further aligning with the methodological needs established in Task 1.3.

All identified methods and tools will be systematically considered in Task 1.6 alongside the methodological needs identified through SUSTAIN-HS. This exercise will support the prioritisation of innovative methods that address the most pressing needs of HTA bodies. Methods and tools deemed priorities will be recommended for implementation or further development, with the potential for real-world testing as case studies within the SUSTAIN-HTA Sandbox Environment (SUSTAIN-SB).

The findings underscore the potential role of the SUSTAIN-HTA methods observatory (SUSTAIN-OBS) as a structured and accessible platform for enhancing the visibility and accessibility of innovative HTA methods and tools. By systematically cataloguing methods, the observatory enables HTA bodies to efficiently identify relevant methods and tools that meet their needs and

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 13/16

ensures that advancements in HTA methods and tools are widely disseminated to the broader HTA community.

Despite the structured approach taken in identifying and categorising HTA methods, several limitations should be considered. This report is restricted to research projects funded by specific EU-funded schemes, meaning that methodological advancements from other EU-funding schemes, non-EU programmes, or industry-led efforts were not captured. The reliance on publicly available documentation on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal and projects’ websites introduces the possibility of missing outputs that were not reported. Furthermore, the relevance of the identified methods and tools to HTA bodies may vary depending on institutional contexts, regulatory frameworks, and national HTA priorities, limiting the generalisability of the findings across different European HTA bodies.

5 Next Steps

The next phase of Task 1.5 will focus on enhancing the comprehensiveness and usability of SUSTAIN-OBS. The database will be periodically updated to incorporate new methods and tools emerging from ongoing Horizon Europe and IHI projects, as well as from (completed) EU projects funded under other schemes. Beyond EU-funded initiatives, the observatory will be further expanded by integrating additional sources of methodological advancements, including non-EU programmes, HTA bodies, cross-country HTA collaborations, HTA–payer collaborations, and international (professional) HTA-related organisations. A systematic literature review will also be conducted to capture HTA methods and tools documented in peer-reviewed literature. This multi-source approach will help ensure that the observatory remains comprehensive and reflective of the latest developments in HTA methodology.

A key focus of this phase will involve the development of an online tool to facilitate direct access to the database, allowing users to efficiently search, locate, and retrieve information on innovative HTA methods and tools suited to their specific needs in a structured and user-friendly manner. To enhance the practical utility of the observatory, engagement with HTA bodies will continue, informing the design of the online tool and ensuring that the observatory remains responsive to their evolving needs. Additionally, SUSTAIN-HTA will establish systematic and formal connections with the HTA Coordination Group (HTACG), particularly its Methodology Subgroup, to ensure that the observatory serves as a trusted and enduring resource informing the development and updating of the EU HTA-R methodological guidelines. The Expert Forum will also be regularly consulted for feedback and input on methods development, including their own contributions and

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation	Version: 3.0	
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch	Dissemination: PU	14/16

those of others, to ensure the database remains relevant to ongoing methodological advancements in the field.

Through these steps, the observatory will continue to evolve as a dynamic repository that not only tracks methodological advancements but also facilitates their integration into HTA practice, thereby supporting the effective implementation of HTA across Europe.

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 15/16

References

- Bennett, A., Manca, A., & Patton, T. (2024). *D.1.11—Report on comparison of treatment effects in real life for MDS patients using the EUMDS registry*. HTx. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/grants/docs/080166e50d0bab1e/Attachment_0.pdf
- Chalkou, K., Hamza, T., Benkert, P., Kuhle, J., Zecca, C., Simoneau, G., Pellegrini, F., Manca, A., Egger, M., & Salanti, G. (2024). Combining randomized and non-randomized data to predict heterogeneous effects of competing treatments. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 15(4), 641–656. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1717>
- Cicchetti, A., Di Brino, E., Basile, M., & Filippo, R. (2021). *D9.1—Algorithm for the estimation of the fiscal impact of new technologies*. IMPACT HTA. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/grants/docs/080166e5e562b7ff/Attachment_0.zip
- Claire, R., Elvidge, J., Hanif, S., Goovaerts, H., Rijnbeek, P. R., Jónsson, P., Facey, K., & Dawoud, D. (2024). Advancing the use of real world evidence in health technology assessment: Insights from a multi-stakeholder workshop. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 14, Article 1289365. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1289365>
- Elayan, S., Facey, K., Collins, S., Elvidge, J., Garrett, Z., Oortwijn, W., Mun, L. van, & Goettsch, W. (2024). *D1.1 – Taxonomy Report* (pp. 1–97). SUSTAIN-HTA.
- Elayan, S., Facey, K., Collins, S., Garrett, Z., Salih, F., Knies, S., Schuitmaker, F., & Goettsch, W. (2025). *D1.2 – First Yearly Methodological Needs Overviews* (pp. 1–42). SUSTAIN-HTA.
- Germeni, E., & Szabo, S. (2023). Beyond clinical and cost-effectiveness: The contribution of qualitative research to health technology assessment. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 39(1), Article e23. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0266462323000211>
- Lampe, K., Mäkelä, M., Garrido, M. V., Anttila, H., Autti-Rämö, I., Hicks, N. J., Hofmann, B., Koivisto, J., Kunz, R., Kärki, P., Malmivaara, A., Meiesaar, K., Reiman-Möttönen, P., Norderhaug, I., Pasternack, I., Ruano-Ravina, A., Räsänen, P., Saalasti-Koskinen, U., Saarni, S. I., ...

	D1.7 – First yearly overview HTA methods		
	WP1 – Identification, Synthesis & Prioritisation		Version: 3.0
	Authors: Saif Elayan, Karen Facey, Wim Goettsch		Dissemination: PU 16/16

Kristensen, F. B. (2009). The HTA Core Model: A novel method for producing and reporting health technology assessments. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 25(S2), 9–20. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0266462309990638>

O'Rourke, B., Oortwijn, W., Schuller, T., & Group, the I. J. T. (2020). The new definition of health technology assessment: A milestone in international collaboration. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 36(3), 187–190. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0266462320000215>

Pokhilenko, I., Janssen, L. M. M., Paulus, A. T. G., Drost, R. M. W. A., Hollingworth, W., Thorn, J. C., Noble, S., Simon, J., Fischer, C., Mayer, S., Salvador-Carulla, L., Konnopka, A., Hakkaart van Roijen, L., Brodzky, V., Park, A.-L., & Evers, S. M. A. A. (2023). Development of an Instrument for the Assessment of Health-Related Multi-sectoral Resource Use in Europe: The PECUNIA RUM. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy*, 21(2), 155–166. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40258-022-00780-7>

Sculpher, M. (2008). Subgroups and Heterogeneity in Cost-Effectiveness Analysis. *PharmacoEconomics*, 26(9), 799–806. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00019053-200826090-00009>